

TEACHING FOREIGN LANGUAGE USING COMPUTER TECHNOLOGIES

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The student needs to verify the educational complexes available are constantly corrected and indicate defects in the training materials; secondly, educational material should also develop in accordance with changes in grammatical and lexical phenomena; thirdly, the lack of funding does not allow to urgently change existing training systems of foreign language. Therefore, the problem of modernization of the educational complex(CMD) falls on the shoulders of the student.[1]The process of learning English is a complex, constantly evolving system. Computerization of a foreign language teaching helps facilitate access to information and reduce language learning time. At the moment there is a huge selection of multimedia products, Internet pages containing information necessary for learning a foreign language, electronic textbooks, databases with thematic texts and exercises. A large number of sources makes it difficult to find the necessary information. At the moment, every educator can't deal with existing Multimedia programs and include them in the learning process. Many universities and schools use computer technology and software for teaching IJ, which the market offers, but such multimedia products are not enough to meet: the program of the university or school, the tasks of the teacher, and the needs of the student, student. In each institution of higher learning, teaching a foreign language proceeds differently, depending on the future profession of the student, the depth of study of IJ, the level of mastery of the foreign language, and the tasks of the teacher.[2]

Currently, there are many opinions about whether to use a computer in teaching a foreign language or not. Some believe that the computer should replace the teacher, while others - the computer is not able to present the material as the teacher does. In our opinion, a computer should serve as an auxiliary tool, like any other technical training tool or textbook. We should not forget that a computer has several advantages: it combines video and audio information, text information, the ability to record your own voice and further self-correction of pronunciation. The computer provides great opportunities to test the level of knowledge of a foreign language or topic, without or with the partial participation of a teacher, which will reduce the time of checking the results. For example: "Listen carefully to

the replica and type it exactly as it was said," the computer will check the correct answers in accordance with the template and write the results to the database. We highlight the main methodological functions implemented by computer:

- Informative - the main advantage of a computer is the ability storage and processing of large volumes of information, therefore PCs are widely used in the process of teaching languages as an information system;
- Training - the use of a computer for training in order to form.

Until recently, strong skills remained the main area for the introduction of computer technology in the educational process in the field of information technology. Even some advantages of a personal computer compared to a teacher in the process of training and consolidating educational material.[3]

As a tool for the activities of trainees and trainers, the computer is used in the educational process in the field of information technology primarily to obtain information and technical support. In addition, educators can use PCs as a tool for their professional activities. The functions of a computer as a tool for the learning activities presented above are based on its ability to accurately record facts, store and transmit a large amount of information, grouping and statistical data processing. This allows you to use it to optimize learning management, increase the efficiency and objectivity of the educational process while significantly saving the teacher's time.

We have worked at the theme and came to the following conclusions:Using digital technology in learning a foreign language has become a real necessity nowadays. This research paper has reviewed briefly how digital technology can be utilized in developing the language skills of the learner. Different methods for using digital technology in improving the four language skills were discussed thoroughly. The questionnaire carried out to estimate the acceptability of some students for the utilization of digital technology to enhance their language skills.[4] We cannot imagine a modern lesson without the use of information digital technology. ICT has become an indispensable tool in improving the students' interest to study the problems and develops visual-figurative thinking

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